

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 11: Minor update on random number generators

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Abstract

This mini-tutorial discusses new updates related to random number generators.

Keywords: JECDM, random number generator

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1. Introduction

This mini-tutorial discusses a few updates to the *IRandom* interface, which standardizes the functionalities offered by the framework's Random Number Generators (RNGs). It is, however, imperative to note that the framework does not provide implementations of the generators itself. Instead, it employs the free-to-use *Apache Commons RNG* library for this purpose, which offers a variety of state-of-the-art generators. Regarding the update, it primarily concerns the parallelization of random number generator (RNG) usage, a well-known issue in the literature. When simultaneously using RNGs in, e.g., simulations, it is imperative to ensure that the outcomes are not correlated and are truly random (to a satisfactory extent). For this purpose, the generators offered by the *Apache Commons RNG* library enable the creation of RNG streams, either by advancing their states (jumpable) or by splitting them into child objects (splittable; see the library's documentation for details). In JECDM, the RNGs utilize these functionalities. Specifically, the *IRandom* interface now introduces methods dedicated to these operations (see Listing ??). They are then suitably implemented in the framework's generators, which are simple wrappers to the generators offered by the *Apache Commons RNG* library (note that currently only a few selected generators are wrapped (see *Utils.random* package); also note that not all such generators offer to make jumps or to execute splitting). In what follows, examples of uses of these new methods are showcased.

Listing 1: Mew method signatures + return types in *IRandom* interface

```
/**
 * Method for indicating whether the
 * concrete implementation supports
 * performing jumps; for parallel
 * computations
 * (see {@link IRandom#
 * createInstanceViaJump()}).
 *
 * @return true, if object is jumpable; false
 * otherwise
 */
boolean isJumpable();

/**
 * The method is supposed create object
 * instance with advanced state. The
 * method should return null
 * if {@link IRandom#isJumpable()} returns
 * false.
 *
 * @return object clone with advanced state
 * (null, if the object is not jumpable)
 */
IRandom createInstanceViaJump();

/**
 * The method is supposed create object
 * instance with advanced state. The
 * method should return null
 * if {@link IRandom#isJumpable()} returns
 * false.
 *
 * @param streamSize stream size (the
 * number of clones to construct)
 * @return object clones with advanced
 * state (null, if the object is not
 * jumpable)
 */
```

```

Stream<IRandom> createInstancesViaJumps(int
    streamSize);
25
/**
 * Method for indicating whether the
    concrete implementation supports
    performing the split of the random
    number
 * generator; for parallel computations (
    see {@link IRandom#createSplitInstance
    ()}).
 *
 * @return true, if object is splittable;
30     false otherwise
 */
boolean isSplittable();

/**
35 * The method is supposed create split
    instance of the object. The method
    should return null
 * if {@link IRandom#isSplittable()}
    returns false.
 *
 * @return split object (null, if the
    object is not splittable)
 */
40 IRandom createSplitInstance();

/**
 * The method is supposed create split
    instance of the object. The method
    should return null
 * if {@link IRandom#isSplittable()}
45     returns false.
 *
 * @param streamSize stream size (the
    number of clones to construct)
 * @return split object (null, if the
    object is not splittable)
 */
Stream<IRandom> createSplitInstances(int
    streamSize);

```

```

{ // Using 64-bit Mersenne Twister
    generator
    System.out.println("MersenneTwister64");
    IRandom R = new MersenneTwister64(0); //
        Construct an RNG
    // R = new MersenneTwister64(new long
        []{0, 0, 0}); // multiple seeds can be
        provided; see the java doc for the
        native seed size
5    System.out.println(" Is splittable = " +
        R.isSplittable());
    System.out.println(" Is jumpable = " + R
        .isJumpable());

    Stream<IRandom> newRNGs = R.
        createSplitInstances(10); // creates
        instances via split (only if supported
        by the wrapped RNG)
    System.out.println(" " + newRNGs); // is
        null, as MersenneTwister64 is not
        splittable
10    //IRandom newRNG = R.createSplitInstance
        (); // or create just one instance;
        still null in this case

    newRNGs = R.createSplitInstances(10); //
        creates instances via split (only if
        supported by the wrapped RNG)
    // IRandom newRNG = R.createSplitInstance
        (); // or create just one instance
    System.out.println(" " + newRNGs); // is
        null, as MersenneTwister64 is not
        splittable
15    //IRandom newRNG = R.
        createInstanceViaJump(); // or create
        just one instance; still null in this
        case
}

{
    // Using L32_X64_MIX generator
    System.out.println("L32_X64_MIX");
    IRandom R = new L32_X64_MIX(0); //
        Construct an RNG
    System.out.println(" Is splittable = " +
        R.isSplittable());
    System.out.println(" Is jumpable = " + R
        .isJumpable());

    Stream<IRandom> newRNGs = R.
        createSplitInstances(10);
25    int instance = 0;
    System.out.println(" Split case:");
    for (IRandom r : newRNGs.toList())
    {
        double[] d = r.nextDouble(10);
        System.out.println(" Random doubles
            for instance = " + (++instance) + "
            : "
            + PrintUtils.getVectorOfDoubles(d, 4)
            );
30    }
    newRNGs = R.createInstancesViaJumps(10);
}

```

2. New functionalities

Source package: *t11.t20.t11_rngs.Tutorial1*

This brief tutorial code examines the new basic functionalities presented in Listing ???. For this purpose, the code examines two RNGs: *MersenneTwister64* and *L32_X64_MIX*, checks whether they are jumpable or splittable, and – if so – creates several streams and requests the creation of arrays of random doubles. The code is commented and straightforward and is presented for convenience in Listing ??? for examination. Also, Figure ??? presents the expected console output.

Listing 2: Creating RNG streams

```

MersenneTwister64
Is splittable = false
Is jumpable = false
null
null
L32_X64_MIX
Is splittable = true
Is jumpable = true
Split case:
  Random doubles for instance = 1 : 0,6624 0,4952 0,4491 0,9387 0,2848 0,8050 0,5328 0,5967 0,7527 0,9327
  Random doubles for instance = 2 : 0,7927 0,7888 0,0748 0,2184 0,1639 0,0771 0,5540 0,4403 0,4656 0,5807
  Random doubles for instance = 3 : 0,8352 0,9687 0,7134 0,5522 0,5885 0,8603 0,9117 0,7536 0,9292 0,9986
  Random doubles for instance = 4 : 0,7816 0,4269 0,7558 0,3164 0,6267 0,4199 0,2688 0,0228 0,6667 0,1709
  Random doubles for instance = 5 : 0,3166 0,5912 0,2208 0,7723 0,5297 0,7223 0,6447 0,7562 0,8101 0,6574
  Random doubles for instance = 6 : 0,4927 0,1632 0,6311 0,9578 0,3038 0,4636 0,1963 0,3450 0,0679 0,6990
  Random doubles for instance = 7 : 0,2242 0,1896 0,1261 0,8205 0,5975 0,7811 0,8993 0,3800 0,4419 0,1047
  Random doubles for instance = 8 : 0,3936 0,0019 0,0784 0,2851 0,7989 0,6116 0,4380 0,2318 0,4010 0,3590
  Random doubles for instance = 9 : 0,5833 0,8167 0,0076 0,1562 0,9116 0,3460 0,7080 0,1768 0,8375 0,9510
  Random doubles for instance = 10 : 0,9746 0,6950 0,9696 0,5342 0,0792 0,5634 0,9988 0,4912 0,0745 0,2874
Jump case:
  Random doubles for instance = 1 : 0,8673 0,9234 0,3314 0,2308 0,5661 0,6510 0,1521 0,7043 0,3591 0,5356
  Random doubles for instance = 2 : 0,6563 0,2627 0,8027 0,8656 0,6073 0,1246 0,4157 0,5343 0,0000 0,0618
  Random doubles for instance = 3 : 0,2995 0,7257 0,3008 0,5848 0,7560 0,0513 0,9651 0,8766 0,7654 0,9130
  Random doubles for instance = 4 : 0,5998 0,1298 0,3581 0,0385 0,5677 0,6770 0,4091 0,1624 0,8402 0,0172
  Random doubles for instance = 5 : 0,6272 0,1299 0,2789 0,0792 0,0270 0,5228 0,3343 0,2647 0,1303 0,7348
  Random doubles for instance = 6 : 0,4811 0,2363 0,6839 0,3172 0,1202 0,6711 0,0058 0,2729 0,6338 0,6836
  Random doubles for instance = 7 : 0,0905 0,8548 0,8236 0,7314 0,1525 0,7997 0,7164 0,0445 0,2964 0,8380
  Random doubles for instance = 8 : 0,7112 0,5345 0,1810 0,6922 0,3782 0,5746 0,5404 0,5235 0,6466 0,8111
  Random doubles for instance = 9 : 0,6524 0,0473 0,3480 0,4912 0,1222 0,6410 0,1114 0,3348 0,1049 0,6696
  Random doubles for instance = 10 : 0,1623 0,6843 0,3608 0,3720 0,7452 0,6986 0,1079 0,0466 0,0237 0,7323

```

Figure 1: Expected console output

```

instance = 0;
System.out.println("  Jump case:");
for (IRandom r : newRNGs.toList())
{
  double [] d = r.nextDouble(10);
  System.out.println("    Random doubles
    for instance = " + (++instance) + "
    : "
    + PrintUtils.getVectorOfDoubles(d, 4)
    );
}
}

```

options are summarized in the tutorial's source code, which is delivered in Listing ?? for convenience.

Listing 3: Creating RNG streams in experiments

```

// Create GDC via params container, as
// usual:
GlobalDataContainer.Params pGDC = new
GlobalDataContainer.Params();

// [...] Here comes some configuration

// Configure Random Number Generator
// Initializer (RNGI):
{
  // Example 1: This initializer
  // instantiates a specified RNG given an
  // input seed for the trial data
  // container
  // being currently instantiated. The seed
  // is set by the experiment executor at
  // the global level, and it is
  // defined as: current scenario ID (i.e.,
  // 0, 1, 2, ... ) * no.trials + current
  // trial ID (i.e., 0, 1, 2, ... ),
  // producing thus non-colliding,
  // sequential seeds.
  //pGDC._RNGI = new
  DefaultRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer
  (seed -> new MersenneTwister64(seed));
pGDC._RNGI = new
  DefaultRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer
  (MersenneTwister64::new); // or using

```

3. Configuring the random number generation initializer in experiments

Source package: `t11_t20.t11_rngs.Tutorial2`

Creating streams can now be exploited during experimentation. When employing *ExperimentExecutor* to perform the experiment, several trials may be executed simultaneously. By default, these trials, when run, are supplied with instances of RNGs initialized with sequential and non-colliding seeds. Now, however, this process is more configurable and can exploit the jumpable/splittable RGN stream creation. As for this option, the RNG batches can be instantiated at the global or scenario level and accordingly delivered to the trial being run. If further adjustments are needed, one can implement a dedicated initializer instead of using the delivered implementations. These three

```

    the method reference
}
{
// Example 2: This initializer constructs
// streams of RNGs using IRandom.
// createSplitInstances(...), or
// IRandom.createInstancesViaJumps(...)
// methods, depending on the selected
// mode
// (FromStreamsInitializer.Mode.
// SPLITTABLE/JUMPABLE flag). The streams
// are created either globally
// (all required instances are created at
// once; see the FromStreamsInitializer.
// InitializationStage.GLOBAL
// flag) or at the scenario level (only
// scenario-related batched are created,
// determined by the number of
// trials specified; see the
// FromStreamsInitializer.
// InitializationStage.SCENARIO flag).
// The below
// constructor must also be supplied with
// the reference RNG instance from which
// the streams will be created.
pGDC._RNGI = new FromStreamsInitializer(
    FromStreamsInitializer.Mode.SPLITTABLE,
    FromStreamsInitializer.
        InitializationStage.GLOBAL,
    () -> new L32_X64_MIX(0));
}
{
// Example 3: Alternatively, one can
// create own RNGs provided by
// implementing the interface:
pGDC._RNGI = new
    IRandomNumberGeneratorInitializer()
{
/**
 * This method can be implemented to
 * create streams during GDC
 * initialization.
 * @param noScenarios total number of
 * scenarios (should include even
 * disabled ones)
 * @param noTrials total number of
 * trials per scenario
 * @throws GlobalException an exception
 * can be thrown and can be handled
 * by the executor
 */
@Override
public void
    requestStreamsCreationDuringGDCInit(
        int noScenarios, int noTrials)
        throws GlobalException
{

}

/**
 * This method can be implemented to

```

```

    create streams during SDC
    initialization.
 * @param scenario scenario being
    processed
 * @param noTrials total number of
    trials per scenario
 * @throws ScenarioException an
    exception can be thrown and can be
    handled by the executor
 */
@Override
public void
    requestStreamsCreationDuringSDCInit(
        Scenario scenario, int noTrials)
        throws ScenarioException
{

}

/**
 * This method must be implemented to
 * return a dedicated, i.e., trial-
 * specific, RNG.
 * @param scenario trial's scenario
 * requesting the random number
 * generator
 * @param trialID ID of a trial
 * requesting the random number
 * generator
 * @param noTrials total number of
 * trials per scenario
 * @return a dedicated RNG instance
 * @throws ScenarioException an
 * exception can be thrown and can be
 * handled by the executor
 */
@Override
public IRandom getRNG(Scenario scenario
    , int trialID, int noTrials) throws
    ScenarioException
{
    return null;
}
};
}

```